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D4.4

Final Report on Trustworthy and Efficient Digital Components

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Abstract

This deliverable concludes the COREnext work on trustworthy and efficient digital components for Beyond-5G and 6G networks. Building on the concepts and components introduced in D4.1, heterogeneous acceleration developments as presented in D4.2, and trustworthiness mechanisms for computation and orchestration discussed in D4.3, it now reports the final status of all components. For each building block we present the prototype maturity, achieved KPIs, and interactions across partners, together with their integration paths towards the upcoming demonstrators in WP6. The deliverable also outlines the research outlook and road to product, linking the technical results to the project's exploitation plan. It thereby provides the complete picture of how COREnext digital components advance efficient processing and trustworthy execution for 6G.

Keywords

6G, RAN processing chain, RISC-V accelerators, heterogeneous computing, forward error correction (FEC), MAC scheduling, orchestration, isolation, virtualization, microkernel (M³), FPGA multi-tenancy, DSP virtualization, IoT trust management, radio link authentication, efficiency, trustworthiness

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Contributing Partners

Abbreviation	Company name
BI	BARKHAUSEN INSTITUT
EAB	ERICSSON
CYB	CYBERUS TECHNOLOGY
EUR	EURECOM
WINGS	WINGS ICT SOLUTIONS
ETHZ	EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH
IHP	IHP MICROELECTRONICS
NNF	NOKIA NETWORKS FRANCE
IIIV	NNF/IIIV LABS
IFAT	INFINEON TECHNOLOGIES
KAL	KALRAY
EF	ERICSSON FRANCE
TUD	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET DRESDEN

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Executive Summary

This deliverable D4.4 presents the final results of COREnext Work Package 4 on trustworthy and efficient digital components for Beyond-5G and 6G networks. It concludes the work of D4.1 (concepts), D4.2 (heterogeneous acceleration), and D4.3 (trustworthy computation and orchestration), and serves as the final technical report before the integration into WP6 and WP7. The components covered are:

Heterogeneous Acceleration for Efficient Processing:

- Programmable Many-Core RISC-V Accelerator for PHY Processing: TeraPool
- Programmable Vector Processing Accelerator
- FEC Accelerator
- MAC Scheduling Accelerator

Trustworthy Computation and Orchestration:

- FPGA Multi-Tenancy
- Digital Signal Processor Virtualization
- M³ Microkernel-Based System
- IoT Management
- Radio Link Authentication

For each of these components, the deliverable reports on:

Finalized Component and Prototype Status

- Description of the achieved design maturity, available prototypes, and implementation progress.

Achieved KPIs

- Summary of performance, efficiency, and trustworthiness targets met, with quantitative indicators, where available.

Component / Partner Interactions and Input to WP6

- Identification of partner roles, interfaces, and how each single component provides input for later demonstrators.

Research Outlook / Road to Product

- Discussion of open research challenges, technical next steps, and potential pathways for evolving prototypes towards product readiness.

This deliverable therefore provides the consolidated picture of all digital components developed in WP4 and sets the technical foundation for their upcoming integration and exploitation in the following work packages.

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Acronyms and Definitions

WP	Work Package	NOMA	Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access
5G	Fifth Generation	NR	New Radio
6G	Sixth Generation	OAuth	Open Authorization
AI	Artificial Intelligence	OFDM	Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing
CNN	Convolution Neural Network	OFDMA	Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiple Access
CP	Cloud Provider	OPS	Operations per Second
CP	Cyclic Prefix	O-RAN	Open Radio Access Network Alliance
CRC	Cyclic Redundancy Check	OSR	Oversampling Ratio
DMA	Direct Memory Access	PA	Power Amplifier
DNN	Deep Neural Network	PBO	Power Back-Off
DPU	Data Processing Unit	PDCP	Packet Data Convergence Protocol
DRAM	Dynamic Random Access Memory	PHY	Physical Layer
DRL	Deep Reinforcement Learning	PUSCH	Physical Uplink Shared Channel
DSP	Digital Signal Processor	QAM	Quadrature Amplitude Modulation
DU	Distributed Unit	QoS	Quality of Service
FEC	Forward Error Correction	RAN	Radio Access Network
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform	RISC-V	Reduced Instruction Set Computer V
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Array	RLC	Radio Link Control
IoT	Internet-of-Things	RRC	Radio Resource Control
IP	Intellectual Property	RRM	Radio Resource Management
ISA	Instruction Set Architecture	RU	Remote Unit
KPI	Key Performance Indicators	SDR	Software Defined Radio
LDPC	Low Density Parity Check	SIMD	Single-Instruction Multiple-Data
LLR	Log-Likelihood Ratio	TA	Trusted Authority
LTE	Long Term Evolution	TCDM	Tightly Coupled Data Memory
MAC	Media Access Control	TCU	Trusted Communication Unit
MIMO	Multiple Input Multiple Output	TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
ML	Machine Learning	TTI	Transition Time Interval
MMSE	Minimum Mean Squared Error	UE	User Equipment
MPSoC	multi-processors system-on-chip		

1 Introduction

The evolution from 5G to Beyond-5G and 6G networks will enable new classes of applications such as extended reality (XR), autonomous driving, industrial automation, and large-scale IoT infrastructures. These use cases, first defined in Deliverable D2.1, pose stringent requirements: ultra-low latency, massive connectivity, high reliability, energy efficiency, and strong guarantees of trustworthiness. Addressing these challenges requires a holistic design approach, spanning efficient digital signal processing, innovative hardware architectures, and built-in mechanisms for isolation and secure execution.

The **COREnext** project tackles these challenges by developing a disaggregated and trustworthy computing architecture for 6G. Building on the use cases and requirements defined in WP2, Deliverable D3.1 translated them into a system-wide architecture. This architecture combines heterogeneous acceleration, efficient interconnects, and mechanisms for trust and attestation into a coherent platform. It identifies a set of analogue and digital components as building blocks developed in Work Packages 4 and 5, which in turn provide input back into the architectural evolution and to the system-level validation in WP6.

Within this framework, **Work Package 4 (WP4)** focuses on the digital components. Its dual objectives are (i) to design heterogeneous hardware accelerators that enable energy-efficient and programmable processing across the radio access network (RAN), and (ii) to develop mechanisms for trustworthy computation and orchestration that guarantee isolation and secure execution across heterogeneous resources. Together, these digital building blocks form the foundation for demonstrators in WP6 and for the exploitation and innovation activities in WP7.

The work in WP4 has been structured into a sequence of deliverables:

- **D4.1** “Concept for Hardware Security Primitives and Heterogeneous Acceleration” introduced the architectural foundations, identifying RISC-V-based accelerators as enablers for power-efficient processing, and outlining hardware security primitives to support isolation and orchestration.
- **D4.2** “Heterogeneous Acceleration for Efficient Processing” reported progress on the accelerator components, including a programmable many-core RISC-V accelerator, a vector processor, a forward error correction (FEC) accelerator, and a MAC scheduling accelerator. It also presented quantitative KPIs on performance and efficiency.
- **D4.3** “Trustworthy Computation and Orchestration” presented mechanisms to provide trustworthiness at different levels, including FPGA multi-tenancy, DSP virtualization, the M³ microkernel-based system, IoT management, and radio link authentication, with their prototype status and trustworthiness KPIs.

This deliverable, **D4.4** “Final Report on Trustworthy and Efficient Digital Components”, concludes the work of WP4. It consolidates the final prototype status of all components, summarizes their achieved KPIs, reports on their role in partner interactions and input to WP6 demonstrators, and outlines research outlooks and roadmaps towards product readiness.

The remainder of this document is structured as follows: Chapter 2 describes the COREnext platform architecture and its layered processing model, drawing from D2.1, D3.1, and D4.1. Chapter

3 recaps the main contents of D4.2 and D4.3 in more detail, including achieved KPIs, and prepares the ground for the final results. Chapter 4 presents the finalized WP4 components, structured by prototype status, KPIs, partner interactions/input to WP6, and research outlook/road to product.

2 Processing Layers and COREnext Platform Architecture

The COREnext platform builds on the requirements defined in D2.1, where extended reality (XR), automotive infrastructure, and smart city scenarios were identified as representative 6G use cases. These applications demand extreme performance in terms of latency, throughput, and reliability, while also requiring strong guarantees of trustworthiness and energy efficiency at scale. To address these challenges, D3.1 defined a disaggregated system architecture that combines heterogeneous acceleration, efficient interconnects, and mechanisms for isolation and attestation into a coherent and trustworthy platform.

This architecture is both heterogeneous and disaggregated. It combines general-purpose processors with domain-specific accelerators, deployed across radio units (RUs), distributed units (DUs), and central units (CUs). It also embeds trustworthiness mechanisms such as secure orchestration, virtualization, and authentication. The goal is to provide an execution environment that meets the dual objectives of efficiency and trustworthiness, two guiding principles of COREnext.

Figure 1: Overview of digital components

Processing Layers

As introduced in D4.1, the COREnext digital components map naturally onto the processing layers of the RAN (see Figure 1):

- Low-PHY: functions such as FFT/iFFT and beamforming, executed close to the antenna and highly parallelizable.
- High-PHY: channel estimation, equalization, demapping, and FEC coding, requiring high-throughput accelerators.
- MAC: scheduling and resource allocation, involving complex optimization under real-time constraints.

- Higher Layers: orchestration, virtualization, IoT management, and authentication, which ensure that efficiency gains translate into trustworthy system operation.

This layered view highlights the interplay between the two innovation areas: accelerators provide the raw efficiency needed for PHY and MAC, while orchestration and security components ensure trustworthiness across higher layers and towards distributed resources.

Heterogeneous acceleration for efficient signal processing

To meet the processing demands of the 6G radio access network (RAN), WP4 develops accelerators targeting the most compute-intensive functions across the PHY and MAC layers. Building on the concept outlined in D4.1, the approach combines loosely coupled accelerators (standalone application-specific units) with tightly coupled accelerators (extensions to the RISC-V ISA). This hybrid design provides both high efficiency and programmability. The main acceleration components are (see Figure 1):

- Programmable Many-Core RISC-V Accelerator (TeraPool): tailored for highly parallel low-PHY tasks such as FFT/iFFT and beamforming.
- Programmable Vector Processing Accelerator: optimized for data-parallel high-PHY workloads like channel estimation, equalization, and demapping.
- Forward Error Correction (FEC) Accelerator: a dedicated unit addressing the extreme throughput requirements of channel decoding.
- MAC Scheduling Accelerator: designed for intelligent resource allocation in the MAC layer, supporting low latency and high network utilization.

Trustworthy computation and orchestration

Efficiency alone is insufficient; 6G systems must also guarantee confidentiality, integrity, and resilience against malicious actors. WP4 therefore also develops mechanisms to isolate workloads and orchestrate heterogeneous resources securely. Building on the foundations described in D4.1, the orchestration approach spans multiple levels: from sharing a single accelerator among tenants, to managing heterogeneous many-cores, to securing large-scale IoT deployments. The main orchestration and trust components are (see Figure 1):

- FPGA Multi-Tenancy: enabling secure sharing of FPGA-based accelerators between different users.
- DSP Virtualization: providing resource partitioning and flexible allocation of digital signal processors.
- M³ Microkernel-Based System: integrating heterogeneous many-cores with strong hardware-enforced isolation.
- IoT Management: classifying and managing IoT devices with built-in trust indices.
- Radio Link Authentication: leveraging RF fingerprinting and AI-based classification for device authentication.

The next chapter will recap the main results of D4.2 and D4.3 in detail, including achieved KPIs, to prepare the ground for the consolidated final results presented in this deliverable.

3 Summary of Results from D4.2 and D4.3

Following the conceptual introduction in D4.1, the subsequent deliverables reported concrete progress in the development of trustworthy and efficient digital components. D4.2 concentrated on heterogeneous acceleration for efficient processing, while D4.3 addressed trustworthy computation and orchestration. Both deliverables presented prototype implementations and initial KPI evaluations, which are reproduced here in tabular form.

In D4.2, the focus was on the extreme computational demands of 6G PHY and MAC processing. The results confirmed that programmable RISC-V-based accelerators can achieve significant efficiency gains while retaining the flexibility needed for evolving standards. At the same time, dedicated application-specific designs remain indispensable for workloads such as forward error correction, where raw throughput requirements cannot be met otherwise. The main trade-off explored in this work was therefore between programmability and specialization: while programmability accelerates time-to-market and supports long-term reusability, specialization is essential to sustain performance and energy efficiency at scale. Table 1 summarizes these findings, showing latency, throughput, and power consumption results across the various prototypes.

Table 1: Key Performance Indicators per acceleration components

Acceleration Component	KPI	Benefit Measure
Programmable Many-Core RISC-V Accelerator for PHY Processing: TeraPool	Latency and Power Consumption of a 5G-PUSCH TTI	1.72ms @ 5.5W (typical corner, 0.8V, 25°C)
Programmable Vector Processing Accelerator	Speedup of LTE kernels vector implementation vs scalar	Speedup 5 (layer demapping) to 93 (antenna combining)
FEC Accelerator	Throughput	1000Gb/s @2GHz uncoded 1200Gb/s @2GHz coded
MAC Scheduling Accelerator	UE throughput under changing channel conditions, Inference latency	49 μ s @ 1 GHz

D4.3 complemented this work by addressing the equally critical requirement of trustworthiness. Here, the main challenge was to integrate isolation, virtualization, and authentication mechanisms into heterogeneous systems without prohibitive performance penalties. The results showed that multi-tenancy, virtualization, and microkernel-based approaches can provide strong security guarantees with moderate overhead, while higher-layer mechanisms such as IoT trust management and RF-based authentication extend these guarantees across the network. The trade-offs in this work were primarily between trustworthiness and overhead: while additional layers of isolation and security inevitably consume resources, the reported KPIs demonstrated that

these costs can be kept acceptable relative to the gains in confidentiality, integrity, and resilience. Table 2 provides the detailed measurements.

Table 2: Key Performance Indicators per orchestration component

Orchestration Component	Cost Measure	Benefit Measure
FPGA multi-tenancy	FPGA area, latency added by authentication	Increase in FPGA utilization with secure authentication
DSP virtualization	Quality of service: latency added by virtualization	Number of workload instances sharing a DSP
M ³ microkernel-based system	Latency and chip area added by TCU isolation component	Small size of trusted components
IoT Management	Execution time to provide trust index	Efficacy of trust classification for IoT devices
Radio link authentication	Latency and energy usage of classification model	Model classification accuracy and false positive rate

Together, these deliverables established the feasibility of COREnext's dual focus on efficiency and trustworthiness. D4.2 showed that the acceleration of critical PHY and MAC functions can meet the stringent requirements of 6G, while D4.3 demonstrated that such acceleration can be embedded into a trustworthy execution environment.

Building on this foundation, the following chapter presents the final results of D4.4. It details the prototype status of each component, summarizes the achieved KPIs, describes partner interactions and contributions to WP6 demonstrators, and outlines the technical research outlook towards productization.

4 RISC-V-based Acceleration

This chapter presents the final results of the COREnext acceleration components developed for the PHY and MAC layers. Building on the concepts introduced in D4.1 and the progress reported in D4.2, it details the status of the RISC-V-based many-core and vector processors, the FEC accelerator, and the MAC scheduling accelerator. For each, we report prototype maturity, achieved KPIs, partner interactions and input to WP6, and a research outlook towards product readiness.

4.1 Programmable Many-Core RISC-V Accelerator for PHY Processing: TeraPool

WP4 addressed the acceleration of lower-PHY functions by means of a programmable RISC-V Many-Core cluster, namely TeraPool.

4.1.1 Finalized Component and Prototype Status

The finalized version of the design contains 1024 RV32IMA cores with gNB processing extensions: Zfinx, Zhinx, Xsmallfloat, Xpulpimg. The cores share 4MiB of multi-banked scratchpad memory. Thanks to a low-latency hierarchical interconnect any core can access any bank of the design in less than 11-cycles without contentions. This enables a streamlined and user-friendly MIMD programming model, that is particularly suited for large-scale lower-PHY workloads (e.g. FFT, Beamforming, channel-estimation, MMSE Equalization).

The RTL code of TeraPool processors and cores-L1 interconnect, as well as the software for lower-PHY functions acceleration is open-sourced on GitHub¹.

4.1.2 Achieved KPIs

Post placement and routing PPA analyses of the TeraPool cluster show peak 1.79 TFLOPS (FP32), 875 TT operating frequency, 82mm² area footprint in GF12 LPPLUS FinFET technology. In a high load scenario, with 64 antennas, 273PRBs, 32 beams, 4 Layers, the cluster achieves SoA performance for programmable processing engines in representative lower-PHY workloads, namely FFT (150 Gbps), Beamforming (300 Gbps), CHE (45 Gbps), MMSE (10 Gbps). The end-end processing latency for the compute operations in lower-PHY PUSCH is 1.7 ms and requires less than 5.5W².

Table 3 compares our approach to rapidly evolving industry solutions for software-defined 5G processing.

¹ <https://github.com/pulp-platform/mempool>

² <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/11038837>

Table 3: Key Performance Indicators of commercial SoA platforms for software-defined lower-PHY processing

Platform	PHY Processor	ISA	Multi-Core	5G split
NVIDIA AX800	Ampere GPU BlueField-3 DPU	NVIDIA	Yes (8192c)	8
EdgeQ/S-series	TXU Processor ARM Neoverse-E1	RISC-V ARM	Yes (60c)	6-7.2
Picocom/PC802	Ceva XC12	RISC-V	No (25c)	7.2X
Marvell/Octeon10	ARM Neoverse-N2 DSP Processors Accelerators	ARM	Yes (<36c)	7.X
Qualcomm/X100	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	7.X

General-purpose graphic processing units (GP-GPUs) achieve high-performance parallelization and keep software versatility. They are nowadays the main computing platforms for deep learning applications, and they are also considered good options to fill the flexibility/performance gap required by 5G and beyond. In fact, aiming for the reuse of existing GP-GPU cloud infrastructure in the domain of 5G, NVIDIA fostered RAN virtualization³. Wireless processing software libraries with CUDA support were developed to run on commodity cloud hardware, such as the AX800 converged accelerator, which achieves 36.56-Gb/s (downlink) and 4.79-Gb/s (uplink) throughput. With 350-W peak power consumption, AX800 usage is recommended in a cloud infrastructure. GP-GPU-based RAN processing, and therefore, targets 5G split 8, where none of the PHY functions is implemented in the BS, putting high requirements on the data rates of the network fronthaul: 100 Gb/s.

EdgeQ S-Series⁴, Picocom PC802⁵, Marvell Octeon10⁶ and Qualcomm X100⁷ are heterogeneous platforms all containing one or more programmable components. They implement the 5G split

³ <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10310082>

⁴ <https://www.edgeq.io/technology/>

⁵ <https://picocom.com/products/socs/pc802/>

⁶ <https://www.marvell.com/products/data-processing-units.html>

⁷ <https://www.qualcomm.com/news/onq/2023/03/how-we-won-the-acceleration-architecture-debate>

7.X, where the PHY functions up to decoding of the received signals are offloaded to the BS. For all these platforms, vendors offer pre-built libraries of kernels with the hardware. Our approach is aligned with this trend; it can be used to implement a software-defined version of split 7.X and it offers additional advantages. First, it has at least 10× more cores than all the clusters used in industry platforms for deployment at the network's edge. Its processing elements are, however, smaller and architecturally simple. The core complex occupies only 80 kGE and a SubGroup instance, including 64 cores and 1 MiB of memory occupies 2.3 mm² in 12 nm. The ARM Neoverse-N2 in Marvell's Octeon10 is bulkier; a single core occupies 1.3 mm² in 5 nm. Second, it offers competitive power consumption. It consumes 5.54 W on average for PUSCH uplink. This processing is similar to the downlink workload described by [https://www.qualcomm.com/news/onq/2023/03/how-we-won-the-acceleration-architecture-debate], which in turn consumes ~18 W on the X100 card. Third, it proposes an efficient novel shared-memory architecture. The work on TeraPool showed how this can be used to implement an in-line processing pipeline, where the L1 memory is used as a low-latency compute buffer⁸.

4.1.3 Component/partner Interactions and Input to WP6

The post placement and routing PPA analyses on the TeraPool provided in D4.3 are available in the context of WP6 for power and area-cost of programmable acceleration solutions for gNB lower-PHY processing.

4.1.4 Research Outlook / Road to product

Future research directions include and are not limited to:

1. The exploration of RVV ISA-extensions applied to gNB processing, in synergy to TUD results on the WP4 programmable vector accelerator component. The integration of multiple RVV engines in TeraPool was partially explored⁹.
2. The exploration of more area-efficient NoC-based solutions for the cores-L1 memory interconnect, which was partially addressed¹⁰.
3. The integration of domain specific accelerators in the TeraPool Tiles, with the purpose of addressing mixed AI-telecommunications workloads, as foreseen by IMT-2030 agenda¹¹.

⁸ <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/11038837>

⁹ <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/10992996>

¹⁰ <https://arxiv.org/abs/2508.02446>

¹¹ <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-R/study-groups/rsg5/rwp5d/imt-2030/pages/default.aspx>

4.2 Programmable Vector Processing Accelerator

Fixed-function accelerators provide excellent efficiency and performance but are challenging to virtualize. Programmable platforms are more efficient but less efficient in comparison. Our aim is to fill the gap on the performance–flexibility trade–off curve between general-purpose processors and fixed-function accelerators with programmable vector processing accelerators.

Like other single-instruction multiple-data (SIMD) architectures, Vector processors distribute the instruction fetch and decode overhead over a vector of data items. The functional units (FUs) inside then process the data vectors in parallel. They do so in a pipelined fashion—in contrast to conventional so-called “packed-SIMD” extensions. Thus, the former exploit not only data-level but also instruction-level parallelism—a potential for higher utilization of the FUs. Another advantage of the vector approach is its enhanced scalability gained by decoupling the software vector length from the underlying implementation. The same binary can run on a variety of implementations optimized for different key performance indicators.

We set out to improve vector processing instruction set architectures (ISAs) in a way that optimizes chaining, i.e., the pipelined instruction execution inside the vector processor. Our goal is to increase the utilization of the FUs. Increased utilization comes with better performance and potentially lower energy consumption because of reduced leakage. To this end, we take a closer look at the internals of state-of-the-art open-source vector processors running selected communications signal processing kernels and model different vector processor microarchitectures.

4.2.1 Finalized Component and Prototype Status

We made two optimizations to vector processors microarchitectures. Our first optimization proposal is the dual vector load which loads two vectors that are operands to a follow-up binary operation in parallel to bring the execution of the latter instruction forward. Theoretical analysis of this ISA extension showed that it is beneficial for compute-bound and some memory-bound programs. The highest possible speedup is 33 % and we achieved a speedup of 21 % in an implementation with about 2 % area overhead¹².

Our second optimization concerned the vector register file, which we identified as a major bottleneck. The bottleneck is even more severe when vector processor works at a high utilization. To study the problem, we have built a cycle-accurate software model of a vector processor with multiple architectural options. The model allows to study the impact of bank conflicts on the runtime and the utilization of the functional units. We analysed the degradation by and the characteristics of VRF access conflicts thoroughly. If left unmanaged they can easily more than halve the utilization. However, one can manage them by avoidance, resolution, and mitigation. We

¹² <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10121996>

invented dynamic bank layout to overcome the suboptimal conflict avoidance of static bank layouts and an optimized round-robin arbitration for mixed-width arithmetics¹³.

4.2.2 Achieved KPIs

We measured the utilization and runtime of selected vector processing kernels and compared an ideal vector processor and state-of-the-art designs with our optimizations. Overall, our VRF architecture with dynamic bank layout and a width-aware arbitration achieves performance gains for a wide range of vector processor design parameters—especially for long chime lengths—and allows for a trade-off. One can save power and area-hungry operand queues (buffers between the VRF and the FUs) at no performance degradation. One can also keep the deep operand queues and increase the performance and runtime. For an average configuration (eight banks and a vector length that is eight times the processing throughput) we measured an increase of the average utilization from 83 % to 85 %, closer to the 89 % that would be possible with an ideal VRF. This increase corresponds to a performance increase of 3 %. With longer vectors (vector length is 32 times the processing throughput), when utilization is higher, we measured an increase of the average utilization from 87 % to 89 %, closer to the 92 % that would be possible with an ideal VRF. This increase corresponds to a performance increase of 3 %. The results are plotted in Figure 2.

¹³ <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3702002>

Figure 2: Comparison of average utilization for different operand queue (OPQ) depths, number of VRF banks, and chime lengths C (the ratio of vector length and processing throughput). We compare our approach to a basic and a state-of-the-art optimized VRF. The thick line delimits the maximum achievable utilization with an ideal conflictless VRF.

4.2.3 Component/partner Interactions and Input to WP6

A research collaboration is ongoing with ETHZ. ETHZ is exploring the integration of tiny vector co-processors in the ManyCore cluster described in section 3.1. TUD is providing support to extend the co-processors with dual vector-load.

TUD also collaborates with BI to integrate the Ara vector processor¹⁴ into the M3 platform for trustworthy heterogeneous Multi-Processors Systems-on-Chip (MPSoCs), which is used in the WP6 demonstrators.

¹⁴ <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8918510>

4.2.4 Research Outlook / Road to product

We have not implemented the proposed vector processor optimizations as digital circuits, yet. Doing so will yield more accurate insights into the area saving. Our optimizations might need modifications if they elongate the critical path.

4.3 FEC Accelerator

An LDPC accelerator for a microcontroller leverages an unrolled LDPC decoder to achieve high-throughput forward error correction while offloading computationally intensive tasks from the main CPU. Unlike traditional iterative decoders, the unrolled architecture pre-instantiates the full decoding graph in hardware, eliminating the need for control flow and memory accesses for intermediate messages. This results in deterministic low latency and highly parallel processing, which are particularly beneficial for real-time communication systems.

In this configuration, the microcontroller handles protocol-level tasks and system control, while the LDPC accelerator—integrated as a hardware peripheral—executes the decoding process with minimal CPU intervention. The unrolled design enables the accelerator to process multiple bits per clock cycle, significantly reducing the number of cycles per codeword.

Key benefits of such an architecture include:

- Ultra-low latency, critical for time-sensitive applications.
- Scalability to support different code rates and block lengths with configurable parameters.

This makes an LDPC accelerator with an unrolled decoder particularly well-suited for IoT devices, 5G wireless modules, and other embedded systems where both performance and power efficiency are crucial.

4.3.1 Finalized Component and Prototype Status

During the most recent reporting period, IHP introduced code-rate flexibility into the accelerator design. The earlier version of the decoder was limited to operating with a single fixed LDPC code rate. The new implementation features a VHDL core capable of dynamically varying the FEC rate across the range 0.5 to 0.846. For achieving this flexibility, the design employs a 5G-NR LDPC parity-check matrix with dimensions 704×1408 (see Figure 3). This matrix is constructed from base graph 1 using a lifting factor of $Z=32$. Under the 5G-NR specification, the first $2Z=64$ columns are subject to puncturing and are excluded from data transmission. Unlike the standard, our ASIC implementation prioritizes support for multiple code rates over full compliance with the 5G-NR protocol. Puncturing of the first $2Z$ columns is implemented as an optional feature, and for the results presented in this work, it was left disabled. Consequently, the resulting code functions as a basic rate- $\frac{1}{2}$ LDPC code. This configuration, while enabling flexibility, is not entirely standard-compliant and may lead to a slight reduction in E_b/N_0 performance. To accommodate higher code rates, the design integrates hardware-based rate matching, adopting a strategy similar to that employed in 5G-NR LDPC implementations.

Figure 3: A 5G-NR parity-check matrix is utilized to build a fully unrolled LDPC decoder capable of supporting flexible code rates ranging from 0.5 to 0.846.

The $\frac{1}{2}$ -rate parity-check matrix depicted in Figure 3 defines 704 check nodes, where each row specifies how a check node is connected to the corresponding codeword bits. The figure highlights three critical regions, marked with red rectangles, that play distinct roles in enabling code-rate flexibility.

Part A represents the core section of the matrix, consisting of 128 check nodes. This region is highly interconnected, with complex quasi-cyclic dependencies. Any attempt to remove rows or columns here would disrupt the matrix structure. Therefore, this part remains fixed and unaltered, serving as the core check rows.

Part B highlights a diagonal sub-matrix, where each redundancy bit in the codeword is associated with exactly one check node. By selectively disabling check nodes in the rows indexed between 128 and 704, redundancy bits can be removed one by one without affecting the remaining parity relationships—provided the deactivation starts from the rows with the highest indices. This property is crucial for implementing adaptive code rates in hardware.

Part C corresponds to the check nodes linked to the redundancy bits disabled in Part B. When a redundancy bit in Part B is deactivated, the associated check node in Part C is also turned off, maintaining consistency in the decoding process.

The flexible code rate is achieved by sequentially disabling check nodes, each responsible for one redundancy bit. This approach allows for the removal of up to 576 redundancy bits, reducing the original (1408,704) code with $R=0.5$ to an (832,704) code with $R=0.846$. Consequently, the architecture supports 576 distinct code configurations, offering fine-grained rate adjustment across the entire range $0.5 \leq R \leq 0.846$. Importantly, this capability is not limited to the 5G-NR parity matrix. Any parity matrix featuring a single diagonal sub-matrix in its lower-right corner can enable this form of fully flexible code-rate operation.

The hardware mechanism for adjusting the code rate, as outlined earlier, is both simple and efficient to implement. The process involves skipping the computations for any check node whose row index exceeds a configurable threshold provided as an external parameter. This threshold can take any value between 128 and 704, defining which check nodes remain active. Each check node with an index greater than 128 is equipped with a 9-bit comparator, which determines whether the external parameter is higher or lower than the node's index. Based on this comparison, the check node is either enabled or disabled. When disabled, the node remains physically present in the hardware but is functionally bypassed, with all of its output edges forced to zero.

To ensure compatibility across all supported code rates, the decoder's input and output interfaces always accommodate the full set of redundancy bits required for the lowest rate ($R=0.5$). In cases

where certain redundancy bits are not needed (for higher code rates), zeros are inserted in their positions. As a result, the overall hardware complexity remains equivalent to that of a fixed $\frac{1}{2}$ -rate decoder, while enabling full code-rate flexibility through this lightweight control logic. The implemented chip layout is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Floorplan of the implemented rate-flexible unrolled decoder, with highlighted hardware iteration blocks.

4.3.2 Achieved KPIs

This section presents the achieved performance key performance indicators (KPIs).

4.3.2.1 Bit error rate (BER) performance

Figure 5 illustrates the BER performance of the designed chip in comparison with a floating-point simulation. In the high-rate configuration ($R=0.846$), the hardware shows only a ~ 0.2 dB loss relative to the floating-point MATLAB reference. For the $R=0.5$ configuration, however, the hardware implementation requires a longer accumulator in the variable nodes than the high-rate design. This limitation results in an approximate 0.5 dB performance gap compared to the floating-point model. The gap can be minimized by enhancing the variable node architecture. Therefore, further fine-tuning of the unrolled decoder is essential to achieve optimal performance across the entire range of supported code rates.

Figure 5: BER performance of the rate-flexible unrolled decoder.

4.3.2.2 Chip KPI and comparison to the decoders from the literature

Table 4 provides a comparison between our flexible-rate implementation and other state-of-the-art high-speed LDPC decoders reported in the literature. To the best of our knowledge, this work represents the first unrolled LDPC decoder that not only supports dynamic code-rate adjustment but also achieves a throughput in the range of several hundred Gb/s, while offering unprecedented flexibility with respect to code-rate configuration.

Table 4: KPIs comparison for LDPC encoders

	¹⁵	¹⁶	¹⁷	COREnext implementation	
				at $R = 0.846$	at $R = 0.500$
Technology	28 nm FD-SOI	16 nm FinFET (*)	28 nm	28 nm	
Implementation	Place&Route	Place&Route	Place&Route	Place&Route	
Corner	Typical-case	Worst-case	Worst-case	Setup: Worst-case; Hold: Best-case	
Coded throughput	588 Gb/s	1000 Gb/s (**)	1218 Gb/s	962 Gb/s	1628 Gb/s
Inf. throughput	494 Gb/s	833 Gb/s (**)	1015 Gb/s	814 Gb/s	
LDPC Code	(2048, 1723)	(1027, 856)	802.11n (648,540)	5G-NR (832,704)	5G-NR (1408,704)
Code rate	0.841, const.	0.833, const.	0.833, const.	0.846, flexible	0.500, flexible
Number of cores	1	12	1	1	
Algorithm	Finite-Alphabet, Unrolled	Layered, Cores duplication	Min-Sum, Unrolled	Min-Sum, Unrolled	
Flexible Rate	No	No (***)	No	576 steps, range [0.500, 0.846]	
Iterations	5	4	5	5	
Quantisation	3 bit	5 bit	4 bit	4 bit	
Core Area	16.2 mm ²	2.24 mm ²	5.49 mm ²	17.36 mm ²	
Core utilisation	65.9%	69%	36%	35%	
Clock freq.	862 MHz	1000 MHz	1880 MHz	1156 MHz	
Latency	69.6 ns	38 ns	19.68 ns	36.3 ns	
Area efficiency	36 Gb/s/mm ²	446 Gb/s/mm ²	222 Gb/s/mm ²	47 Gb/s/mm ²	
Energy efficiency	Max. 22.7 pJ/b	7.5 pJ/b at 3 dB;	12.74 pJ/b at 4 dB	27.25 pJ/bit	41.88 pJ/bit
SNR at BER = 10 ⁻⁶		≈ 4.9 dB	≈ 4.75 dB	≈ 4.8 dB	≈ 1.9 dB
SNR at BER = 10 ⁻⁷		≈ 5.25 dB	≈ 5.0 dB	≈ 5.05 dB	≈ 2.35 dB

4.3.3 Component/partner Interactions and Input to WP6

Although the implementation of the LDPC accelerator was carried out exclusively by IHP, we actively engaged with our project partners throughout the development process. We regularly sought their feedback, shared intermediate results, and encouraged open communication to ensure alignment with the broader goals of the project. This collaborative approach helped us refine the design and assess its potential relevance to various use cases within the consortium.

In the context of Work Package 6 (WP6), it is important to note that direct integration of the accelerator into a demonstrator is not currently foreseen. However, the developed accelerator offers a high-throughput error correction capability that aligns well with the performance

¹⁵ R. Ghanaatian et al., “A 5 88-Gb/s LDPC Decoder Based on Finite-Alphabet Message Passing,” IEEE Transactions on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems. 2017.

¹⁶ M. Li, V. Derudder, K. Bertrand, C. Desset, and A. Bourdoux, “High-Speed LDPC Decoders Towards 1 Tb/s,” IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems I: Regular Papers, pp. 1–10, 2021,

¹⁷ L. Lopacinski et al., “Ultra high speed 802.11n LDPC decoder with seven-stage pipeline in 28 nm CMOS,” in IEEE 95th Vehicular Technology Conference, 2022, pp. 1–5.

requirements anticipated for next-generation communication systems. As such, it holds significant potential for future integration into the platform envisioned within the scope of this project

4.3.4 Research Outlook / Road to product

The successful development and validation of the rate-flexible unrolled LDPC decoder mark a significant milestone in advancing high-speed error correction technologies. While the current implementation demonstrates outstanding performance in terms of throughput and flexibility, several research and development steps are envisioned to transition this prototype into a commercial-grade product.

4.3.4.1 Short-Term Outlook

In the immediate future, the focus will be on optimizing power efficiency and reducing implementation complexity. Techniques such as advanced clock gating, power gating of inactive nodes, and pipeline optimization will be further explored. Additionally, migrating the design to smaller technology nodes (e.g., 7 nm or 5 nm) is expected to significantly lower energy per bit while maintaining or increasing throughput.

4.3.4.2 Medium-Term Outlook

For broader applicability, the decoder architecture will be extended to support additional LDPC code standards beyond 5G-NR, such as DVB-S2X, Wi-Fi 7, and emerging optical communication standards. Furthermore, integration with microcontrollers and system-on-chip (SoC) platforms will be investigated to create versatile solutions for both embedded and high-performance applications.

4.3.4.3 Long-Term Road to Product

To achieve a market-ready product, the following steps are essential:

- Industrial-Grade Verification – performing exhaustive testing under real-world operating conditions to ensure robustness and reliability, demonstration in network stack.
- Standardization Compliance – ensuring full compatibility with target communication standards and certification requirements.
- System Integration – collaborating with industry partners to integrate the decoder into commercial modems, baseband processors, and network equipment.
- Commercialization – establishing a production pipeline with silicon foundries and defining a cost-effective manufacturing process.

Ultimately, this research paves the way for next-generation LDPC accelerators that combine extreme throughput, dynamic code-rate adaptation, and energy-efficient operation. With further refinement and industrial collaboration, the presented decoder has the potential to become a key enabler for future wireless, optical, and satellite communication systems.

4.4 MAC Scheduling Accelerator

The MAC scheduler is an integral unit of the Data Link Layer (DLL) and is responsible for distributing available physical resources to user equipment (UE) in the network while adhering to given Quality

of Service (QoS) requirements and resource constraints of the cell and connected devices. Naturally, this translates into a multi objective optimization problem whose exact solution is generally intractable. Therefore, heuristics of various sorts are applied in practice, reaching from well-known and simple algorithms such as Round Robin (RR) or Proportional Fairness (PF) to more sophisticated, QoS-aware algorithms like Modified Largest Weighted Delay First (M-LWDF). Another approach is the use of Machine Learning (ML), especially Deep Reinforcement Learning (Deep-RL), to learn even more complex policies with the potential of using the highly constraint resources more efficiently while increasing QoS at the same time.

However, the powerfulness of Deep Learning comes at a high computational cost. Therefore, it is integral to not only test and verify the functionality of the deep scheduler itself but also the inference time of the Artificial Neural Network (ANN) to guarantee that the cell schedule is available in time, that is, before the start of the next communication slot. Hence, we consider the use of a custom, NVDLA-based AI-accelerator and evaluate the performance of our deep scheduler with respect to inference latency.

4.4.1 Finalized Component and Prototype Status

During the course of this project, we developed AIMOS (short for AI Multi Objective Scheduler) a Deep-RL scheduler, that is channel-, buffer-, resource- as well as QoS-aware. To process the heterogeneous information available at the MAC layer, AIMOS employs a deepset-based feature extractor that learns meaningful representations of the features associated with user equipment (UEs) connected to the cell. These representations form the basis for scheduling decisions targeting devices assigned to the bandwidth part under the control of the MAC scheduler. At time slot t , the scheduler implements a mapping $A_t = f_\theta(X_t)$ where X_t aggregates all UE- and cell-level features. The function f_θ is evaluated once, producing the joint allocation for all UEs and resources in the current slot. No per-UE loops, iterative refinement, or post-hoc corrections are performed; the complete schedule is determined in a single forward pass. This one-shot decision process guarantees constant-time schedule generation up to a maximum number N of active devices per slot. This ensures predictable inference latency in real-time operation.

For training and evaluation, AIMOS is integrated with 5G-LENA, an ns-3-based system-level simulator for 5G networks, combined with a modified version of ns3-gym for reinforcement learning integration. The underlying ANN is implemented in PyTorch, which enables straightforward deployment on commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) AI inference accelerators,

To further analyse execution latency and inference throughput, we emulate the ANN forward pass on an EMBER-based simulation of our custom implementation of NVDLA. EMBER is an in-house framework that provides ultra-fast RTL simulations among other capabilities, making it well suited for detailed accelerator evaluation. Our custom NVDLA design differs from the original NVIDIA implementation by separating data and weight buffers, which are unified in the reference design, and by supporting arbitrary batch sizes. These modifications reduce overall area usage, lower power consumption, and shorten critical paths in the design.

4.4.2 Achieved KPIs

4.4.2.1 Inference Latency and Throughput on NVDLA

The achieved inference latency depends on the selected NVDLA configuration parameters, in particular the sizes of the data and weight buffers, the number of elements in each atomic cube (Atomic C), the number of weight cubes (Atomic K), and chosen integer width. For our evaluation, we fixed both the data and weight buffer sizes at 128 KiB and varied the atomic configurations in a consistent manner, comparing 64×64 and 32×32 setups and an integer width of 16 bit.

Latency results are reported for assumed clock frequencies of 750 MHz and 1 GHz. Since the evaluated configurations have not yet been synthesized, the reported values are based on plausible operating points rather than exact synthesis results.

Our assumptions are based on synthesis results for a configuration with Atomic C = 64, Atomic K = 8 (i.e., 64×8), and an integer width of 16 bit, which achieved a clock frequency of 980 MHz (1020 ps). Both weight- and data buffer were set to 128 KiB. These results were obtained via static timing analysis. The design was synthesized using Synopsys Design Compiler v.2020.03 in 22 nm technology, targeting the SSG process corner at a temperature of 125 °C with a low voltage threshold. As no major increase in critical path length is expected when scaling Atomic K, we consider the chosen clock frequencies as realistic.

Figure 6: Inference latency of single AIMOS forward pass on various NVDLA configurations.

As shown in Figure 6, the inference latency target of numerology $\mu = 4$ (slot duration of $62.5 \mu\text{s}$) can be met by the 64×64 configuration for batch sizes of 64 and 128. For numerology $\mu = 3$ the 64×64 setup achieves the latency target across all batch sizes and clock frequencies, whereas the 32×32 configuration only satisfies the target at a batch size of 128. Finally, for numerology $\mu = 2$ the available time budget is sufficiently large to be met by all evaluated configurations and batch sizes.

4.4.2.2 User Equipment Throughput

We evaluate throughput under pedestrian mobility with 64 UEs served by a single gNB over one bandwidth part at 100 GHz carrier frequency and 400 MHz bandwidth using numerology $\mu = 4$. The simulation area is $50 \text{ m} \times 50 \text{ m}$, and we use 3GPP-compliant antenna and channel models. We consider three traffic profiles:

1. Ten UEs are configured with GBR non-conversational video traffic corresponding to 5QI = 2 with a packet delay budget of 300 ms. Among these, five UEs request a guaranteed bitrate of 40 Mbit/s, while the remaining five UEs request 8 Mbit/s.
2. The other 54 UEs are configured with low-latency eMBB traffic corresponding to 5QI = 83 with a packet delay budget of 10 ms and no throughput request.

We compare AIMOS to Round Robin (RR), Maximum Rate (MR) and the Proportional Fairness-based QoS-aware scheduler provided by 5G-Lena (QoS).

Figure 7: Average throughput of three different QoS-profiles. Error bars denote 99% confidence intervals.

Overall, AIMOS achieves slightly higher throughput across all three traffic classes, although the performance differences remain relatively small.

4.4.3 Component/partner Interactions and Input to WP6

Discussions and information exchange were held with Ericsson regarding the potential use of our internal EMBER-based NVDLA profiling tools for evaluating the inference latency of their ML-based Radio Frequency Fingerprinting (RFF) algorithm in embedded systems.

4.4.4 Research Outlook / Road to product

Future research will focus on extending the scope of AIMOS to more diverse use cases, including high-mobility scenarios, operation across different frequency bands, and multi-cell deployments, potentially in combination with Federated Learning. Moreover, the joint governance of multiple bandwidth parts or component carriers by a single scheduler instance may provide significant efficiency gains, particularly when spectrum from both FR1 and FR2 is available. The impact of reward shaping on key performance indicators (KPIs) should also be examined in greater detail, while the derivation of formal guarantees for URLLC traffic remains an open challenge due to its stringent latency and reliability requirements. In addition, the issue of online model updating, and the necessity of such updates to avoid long-term performance degradation, requires study.

Beyond reinforcement learning, the integration of AI with Bayesian inference is a promising direction. Such hybrid approaches could yield performance improvements over classical methods, especially in scenarios where predictability, interpretability, and verifiable guarantees are important.

To address the practical challenges of deployment, integration into a testbed environment should be targeted. This step would allow assessment of system-level interactions, overheads, and compliance with standardization requirements, thereby supporting the transition from research to product readiness.

Finally, the energy consumption aspect must be considered, not only by making AIMOS energy-aware in its scheduling decisions, but also by addressing the computational cost of executing neural networks, which are inherently resource-intensive.

5 Isolation and Orchestration

This chapter consolidates the final results of the trustworthiness components developed in WP4. Expanding on the work reported in D4.1 and D4.3, it describes the mechanisms for secure resource sharing, virtualization, microkernel-based isolation, IoT device trust management, and radio link authentication. Each component is presented with its prototype status, achieved KPIs, interactions and contributions to WP6, and research outlook and road to product.

5.1 FPGA Multi-Tenancy

NNF has contributed to WP4 by providing a hardware trusted execution environment (HWTEE) to enable user multi-tenancy inside FPGA logic for data processing acceleration. Sharing logical resources among multiple users involves securing data being processed by each user with the help of cryptographic algorithms. The proposed HWTEE is a hardware communication wrapper which first initiates cryptographic keys exchange between the tenancies and the FPGA logic. Then, the HWTEE ensures encryption/decryption by minimizing processing time as much as possible.

5.1.1 Finalized Component and Prototype Status

The proposed HWTEE is composed of hardware components (at the FPGA side) and software components (at the server/CPU side). NNF has developed both and are part of the proposed prototype. The specificity of the solution is the use of two levels of encryption/decryption. AES algorithm is used for the encryption/decryption of the data to process (fast and secure). The issue is to share the encryption/decryption AES key from/to the FPGA. To do so, we use Elliptic-curve cryptography (ECC) managed in the HWTEE.

The HWTEE is currently able to:

- Generates True Random Numbers (TRNG)
- Generates ECC pairs of keys from TRNG
- Send ECC public key to the server/CPU
- Decrypt AES key sent from server/CPU with its own ECC private key
- Decrypt data coming from server/CPU
- Encrypt processed data before sending to server/CPU

The software component on its side:

- Initiate key generation requests to the HWTEE
- Encrypt its own AES key with the received ECC public key and send it to the HWTEE

We propose two prototypes. The first one is an implementation of the HWTEE on the RISC-V Carfield platform from ETH Zürich, partner of the project. We have successfully demonstrated the efficiency of our solution by securing data being sent from/to the general-purpose processor to/from the processing accelerator.

The second prototype is the same implementation of the HWTEE but in another processing execution context. This second prototype uses a Xilinx/AMD FPGA acceleration board connected through PCIe bus inside an HPE server.

5.1.2 Achieved KPIs

Despite the increase of FPGA area and latency added by authentication, the proposed solution in the context of COREnext increases FPGA utilization with secure authentication and data sharing among several tenants.

5.1.3 Component/partner Interactions and Input to WP6

The first prototype has been developed on the RISC-V platform from ETH Zürich partners. To succeed in the objective, we contributed to the Carfield project by adding a new FPGA target. The AMD VCU118 board is now part of the open-source code made available on GitHub by ETH Zürich.

5.1.4 Research Outlook / Road to product

The purpose of the development of multi-tenancy in FPGAs is to offer more efficient use of hardware logical resources in cloud and edge cloud infrastructure. Future research topic should explore better FPGA integration in processing data paths of network functions in cloud infrastructure.

5.2 Digital Signal Processor Virtualization

EURECOM (EUR) participated in WP4 by developing experimental tooling enabling seamless testing and evaluation of computation components in realistic scenarios. The open-sourced research oriented mobile network stack Open Air Interface (OAI) was modified in order to enable future seamless integration of novel components following a standard framework. Matured components designed within the scope of COREnext and beyond can then be challenged with OAI in realistic scenarios.

The delivered component is actually an integration of the O-RAN Accelerator Abstraction Layer (AAL) for channel coding in OAI. AAL is a standard interface for the integration of a set of purpose-built accelerators within cloud infrastructures for mobile networks and the software relying on such infrastructures. In other word the AAL framework provides a standard interface for the integration of virtualized and shared accelerators in the OAI network stack.

5.2.1 Finalized Component and Prototype Status

AAL is integrated in OAI by using the Broad Band DeVice (BBDEV) application of the Data-Plane Development Kit, which provides an open-sourced implementation of the interface.

The most general interface for channel coding within OAI was also revised to enable the seamless integration of a variety of implementations. The new interface is broad as it allows the coding or decoding of an entire slot – the largest chunk of radio resource that can be processed at once while respecting latency constraints – in one function call, and includes segmentation, segment concatenation and rate matching. Then implementations gained a significant freedom necessary for optimizations.

This makes OAI an experimental platform enabled with state-of-the-art computing technologies enabling various experimental use cases like technological comparative studies, testing of capabilities and compliance of novel computing architectures.

[OpenAirInterface with the AAL integration is available through EURECOM's Gitlab.](#)

5.2.2 Achieved KPIs

Among the many libraries available for channel coding – the most intensive computing task in the 5G network stack –, AAL is implemented by only one library supporting 3 state-of-the-art accelerators: 2 engineering samples and one commercial product.

One accelerator can be shared by up to 16 network instances. But in practice, the performance of the accelerator may further limit the number of network instances sharing the accelerator. An evaluation of this limit for the accelerators integrated with OAI is being driven by EUR within WP6.

One of the purposes of the channel coding accelerators is to reduce the cost of computing devices dedicated to channel coding in the network by reducing the number of general-purpose CPU cores necessary for a network workload and replacing them with the accelerator. If the device is properly designed, the resource and energy costs of the network with the accelerator are inferior to the costs without the accelerator.

Another purpose of the channel coding accelerator is to achieve a better best-effort processing time than software. The commercial grade accelerator introduced in OAI with AAL gives a significant boost in comparison to the preexisting software implementation. This boost can be illustrated by comparing the best-effort LDPC decoding time of a slot achieved with software and AAL acceleration for some scenarios specified in the standards. This metric is important to consider for determining if the implementation can match the latency requirements enforced by the standard. Table 5 gives as examples these times for some sample cases among the most demanding cases of the standard:

Cases	Software decoding time	AAL decoding time
100 MHz bandwidth, 30 kHz SCS, 8 RX antennas, MCS 20, 5.9 dB SNR	2823 μ s	136 μ s
40 MHz bandwidth, 30 kHz SCS, 4 RX antennas, MCS 2, -2.1 dB SNR	359 μ s	38 μ s
40 MHz bandwidth, 30 kHz SCS, 4 RX antennas, MCS 16, 11.2 dB SNR	1545 μ s	71 μ s

Table 5: Sample LDPC decoding times with software and AAL

A more extensive study of the performance giving a global overview of the performance of the accelerator should be part of the comparative study conducted within WP6.

5.2.3 Component/partner Interactions and Input to WP6

The experimental platform OAI with its capabilities enabled within WP4 as well as the experience gained in performing this enhancement are used in the scope of WP6.

In Task 6.2, the experience gained about accelerator architecture allows us to design a relevant execution scenario for the M3 baseband workload simulation scenario that is tested by the Barkhausen Institute (BI). OAI with AAL also allows us to generate some reference processing times that are compared with the times achieved by the M3 platform while simulating the same task. These materials are used by EUR and BI to author the paper “Hardware-level Isolation of Dataflows for Trustworthy 5G/6G Signal Processing”, which has been submitted to a GLOBECOM workshop. The purpose of the paper is to demonstrate the ability of the M3 platform to perform in executing realistic digital signal processing workloads.

Within the scope of Task 6.3, OAI with AAL enabled is leveraged by EUR to make performance evaluations and technology comparative studies. The purpose of these studies is to better know the real performance achieved by state-of-the-art computing architectures as a reference point for the novel architectures developed by partners, especially Kalray (KAL) with its accelerated RISC-V platform.

5.2.4 Research Outlook / Road to product

The ultimate purpose of the integration of the O-RAN AAL in OAI is to offer an experimental mobile network software that can serve for the testing, comparison and promotion of novel components developed by partners within COREnext and beyond. It is indeed essential for a new computing solution to be broadly advertised, and its capabilities proven to the research and engineering world in order that end-product integrators choose this solution rather than another one.

5.3 M³ Microkernel-Based System

M³ proposes a new system architecture based on a hardware/software co-design. On the hardware side, M³ builds upon a tiled architecture, where each tile is extended by a new hardware component called Trusted Communication Unit (TCU). The TCU both isolated the tiles from each other and allows to selectively establish communication channels for message passing and memory access. On the software side, M³ runs a small microkernel on a dedicated kernel tile, and applications and operating-system services on the remaining user tiles. This reduces the trusted computing base, because the security-critical kernel is kept small and most of the functionality of the operating system (e.g., file systems, network stacks, and drivers) is provided by unprivileged user tiles. User tiles can use existing communication channels, but only the M³ kernel is allowed to establish such channels. By default, no communication channels exist and thus tiles are isolated from each other.

It has been demonstrated before that this design has advantages for heterogeneous platforms due to the common interface for all tiles provided by the TCU, and that all tiles can be efficiently multiplexed among multiple mutually distrusting applications. Furthermore, it has been shown that

M³ offers superior isolation between applications compared to traditional approaches. Within COREnext, we also demonstrated its advantages regarding real-time guarantees and investigated its suitability for future mobile-communication infrastructures that run radio-signal workloads with low latency requirements. We are also in the process of enabling trusted execution environments on M³. The following gives more details on these three topics.

5.3.1 Finalized Component and Prototype Status

Real-time Properties of the M³ Platform

Within COREnext we investigated the real-time properties of the M³ platform. By construction M³ has the advantage that tiles are isolated from each other by the TCU and lack shared caches or TLBs. This reduces timing jitter significantly and enables *local reasoning*: the real-time analysis can be performed locally on a per-tile basis. To investigate this advantage, we measured the jitter for cross-tile communication and compared it with cross-core communication on Linux and the microkernel NOVA. Since communication on M³ bypasses the OS kernel and avoids interrupts, it achieves a significantly lower round-trip latency of about 300–540 cycles on our FPGA platform. This latency is orders of magnitude lower than on Linux (about 16000 cycles) and NOVA (about 7000 cycles). Furthermore, we observed a jitter of about 100 cycles on M³ and 3000–4000 cycles on Linux and NOVA.

We also found that due to the remaining globally shared resources NoC and DRAM, other tiles can influence the performance of memory-intensive workloads on a victim tile by up to a factor of 5. To mitigate this effect and enable local reasoning even in such noisy environments, we added a token-bucket traffic shaper to the TCU, configurable per process. Our measurements showed that limiting background traffic to 8 MiB/s reduces interference to under 1%.

We published these findings on the 30th IEEE Real-Time and Embedded Technology and Applications Symposium (RTAS) in the paper “Core-Local Reasoning and Predictable Cross-Core Communication with M³”.

Hardware-level Isolation for Signal Processing

Figure 8: Performance comparison of the LDPC workload between M³ and an RFSoc.

In a collaboration with EURECOM, we studied whether the M³ platform is suitable to run signal-processing workloads with low-latency requirements. We evaluated the performance of M³ in comparison to a real Radio Frequency System on Chip (RFSoc) featuring eight FEC computation units. On M³, we developed a data-flow framework that allows arbitrary data streams between tiles including fan-in and fan-out. Based on that, we emulated the signal processing workload by replicating the communication pattern and data sizes and spinning for the execution time of the FEC units. As can be seen in Figure 8: Performance comparison of the LDPC workload between M³ and an RFSoc., M³ can run latency-critical workloads in an efficient way that is competitive to state-of-the-art systems. However, due to the different hardware platforms, the results have to be interpreted with a grain of salt.

The results are described in the paper “Hardware-level Isolation of Dataflows for Trustworthy 5G/6G Signal Processing”, which has been submitted to a GLOBECOM workshop.

Core-Independent Trusted Execution Environments

Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) enable secure data processing by isolating a program from all other software on a system. However, current TEEs are often limited to CPUs and tied to a specific instruction set architecture, making them challenging to use in heterogeneous environments. We are therefore designing core-independent TEEs on M³ where the isolation between TEEs is enforced by the TCU – a separate hardware component. We evaluate the implications in terms of performance, hardware costs, and trusted computing base size on our FPGA-based hardware platform.

5.3.2 Achieved KPIs

We have shown that M³ does not only provide low-latency communication across tiles (300-500 cycles roundtrip time), but can also efficiently execute signal-processing workloads, achieving similar results as state-of-the-art hardware. At the same time, M³ provides superior isolation between the individual components of the workload. Finally, the additional isolation was demonstrated to have negligible impact for mobile communication signal processing workloads. We conclude that the latency targets for running the desired digital workloads on M³ has been achieved while maintaining and with TEEs even strengthening its isolation properties. The protection afforded by M³ relies on a Trusted Computing Base that is orders of magnitude smaller than comparable commodity architectures, contributing to its enhanced attack resilience against both software and hardware vulnerabilities.

5.3.3 Component/partner Interactions and Input to WP6

We collaborated with partner EURECOM (EUR) on emulating realistic signal processing workloads on the M³ platform. We are also in discussions with Ericsson (EAB) about running their fingerprinting AI workload on M³. At the point of writing this deliverable, this collaboration with WP5 is still in an exploratory state.

Conceptually, the M³ platform can incorporate the RISC-V and accelerator components developed in WP4 as parts of its tile-based design. Full integration of all results is beyond the scope of

COREnext, but the methods of integrating accelerators has been demonstrated with M³ in earlier publications and acceleration is also part of our work with EURECOM on running signal processing on M³.

For WP6, the security protection and hardware integration aspects of M³ are part of Task 6.2. The project has developed a demonstrator, which was already presented at EuCNC to showcase M³'s unique selling point of protecting a system against vulnerable hardware and software. We intend to extend this demonstrator for the final review. It has also been used repeatedly within BI to present security research results to regulators and other societal stakeholders.

5.3.4 Research Outlook / Road to product

Partner Barkhausen Institute (BI) continues to advance M³ towards higher TRL. We are currently working to scale the platform in two directions: Within a nationally funded projects we are scaling down the hardware footprint to fit for Internet-of-things use cases. Together with industry and research partners, we are also investigating to scale the platform up towards datacentre and DPU applications. We intend to productize M³ at some point, probably within the context of a spin-off company. However, research efforts to further advance the scale and capabilities of M³ are necessary to become competitive with comparative industrial offerings. The trustworthiness awarded by the platform's security properties remains a key advantage, which highlights its roots in European values.

5.4 IoT Management (WINGS)

As highlighted in previous deliverables D4.1, D4.2 and D4.3, IoT has transformed everyday objects into smart, interconnected devices, now embedded in homes, workplaces, and public spaces. With their growing role in critical systems and sensitive data handling, ensuring device trustworthiness, reliability, security, and privacy, is essential for user safety and system integrity. To address this, a Trust Manager component has been developed integrating a trust manager orchestrator, a trust evaluation function and ML grouping techniques among others. Edge IoT devices like drones and collaborative robots (cobots) interact with the Trust Manager Orchestrator to enable secure and efficient operations. After clustering these devices, each group of devices is evaluated using tailored trust metrics. The trust evaluation function calculates a trust index for each device, which is sent to the trust manager orchestrator to maintain an up-to-date trust profile. To optimize performance, computational tasks are offloaded based on each cluster's capabilities—such as processing power, memory, and network strength. The orchestrator then uses the trust index and task requirements to select the most suitable input node, ensuring secure, efficient, and adaptive task execution across the network.

5.4.1 Finalized Component and Prototype Status

The Trust Manager component integrates several key functionalities for IoT device management (see Figure 9). It includes:

- K-means clustering for grouping the devices with similar characteristics to streamline trust evaluation and task assignment.

- Trust manager orchestrator which assigns tasks to the most trustworthy and capable devices in the network.
- Trust evaluation function which calculates a trust index for each device class based on multiple metrics such as:
 - Availability (% of time the device was active and responsive)
 - Reliability (frequency of successful task execution within a time threshold)
 - Security (secure communication, e.g., Transport Layer Security-TLS-enabled communication)
 - Data privacy compliance (e.g., encryption protocols in transmission)
 - Data integrity (e.g., validating right format of values, checking for duplicates, source validation)
 - Energy consumption – efficiency in task handling
 - Battery level of battery-powered devices
 - Multi-connectivity capabilities (4G/5G, Wi-Fi, NB-IoT, BT, etc., with adaptive RAT selection)

Figure 9: Trust Manager Flowchart [D4.3]

Each metric is normalized and is weighted based on its importance and recency of data (using exponential decay to prioritize newer info). The output is a trust score ranged from 0 to 1. These scores together with real-time data related to the performance, resource usage (e.g., CPU, memory), battery life of each device, and topology graph are fed to the trust manager orchestrator to output the optimal placement of computational workloads and tasks to the available devices and servers. The trust manager orchestrator makes decisions based on the trust index, assigning tasks to the most reliable devices and offloading computational tasks to devices that are capable of handling them (based on their resource availability). This component has been demonstrated in a simulated environment with inputs from IoT devices such as drones and cobots as described in the following subsection.

5.4.2 Achieved KPIs

The Trust Manager component has been evaluated under varying task and device scales in a simulated experimental setup. The trust manager component was compared with a baseline load balancing algorithm and the trustworthiness calculated was the sum of the trust scores of the devices chosen each time for the task placement. The experimental setup was 20-100 devices and 20-900 workloads/tasks. As shown in Figure 10, the Trust Manager has demonstrated significant improvements in trust-based orchestration:

- Up to 53% higher trustworthiness in task allocation compared to baseline load balancing approaches.
- Scalability, since it was successfully evaluated with up to 100 devices and 900 tasks.
- Efficiency, having real-time trust index computation using normalized and weighted metrics with exponential decay for recency prioritization.
- Improved performance with increased device diversity, enabling better task-device matching.
- The more the tasks are, the lower the gains observed due to limited solution space and the more the devices are, the higher the gains observed due to richer allocation options.

These KPIs validate the effectiveness of the Trust Manager in enhancing the security, reliability, and efficiency of IoT networks.

Figure 10: Trustworthiness gains for various device and task counts compared to load balancing baseline algorithm.

5.4.3 Component/partner Interactions and Input to WP6

The Trust Manager has been developed primarily by WINGS ICT Solutions, with potential integration into platforms from other project partners. The trust index output can be embedded into other platforms to evaluate connected devices or hardware components.

The component supports WP6 goals by providing a robust mechanism for secure and efficient IoT device orchestration in experimental setups.

5.4.4 Research Outlook / Road to product

The growing role of IoT devices in critical systems and sensitive data handling, calls for device trustworthiness, reliability, security, and privacy, which is essential for user safety and system integrity. The proposed Trust Manager component can be one solution in future evaluation of trustworthiness of devices for integrating a trust manager orchestrator, a trust evaluation function and ML grouping techniques among others. As a result, we foresee that Edge IoT devices like drones and collaborative robots (cobots) interact with the Trust Manager Orchestrator to enable secure and efficient operations. Currently, the solution is experimental and shown as an initial proof of concept but in the future can be part of a product suite for ensuring the trustworthiness.

5.5 Radio Link Authentication

This section explores the use of Machine Learning (ML) techniques for Radio Frequency Fingerprinting (RFF). These techniques have recently become more promising for Physical Layer Security, as advances in ML methods and computational capabilities make RFF more feasible for modern telecommunication systems, including 5G and beyond. The basic background of RFF is that each transmitting device has minor manufacturing imperfections and operation impairments that result in unique, subtle characteristics or discrepancies in the radio signals it emits. Recent advancements in machine learning and artificial intelligence have indeed demonstrated significant effectiveness in extracting subtle patterns from extensive data. These discrepancies, although often very limited, can be measured, processed and detected, allowing to create a ‘fingerprint’ of the device. The hardware impairments can manifest in imperfections such as quadrature imbalance, phase noise, frequency jitter, power amplifier (PA) in-band distortion, intermodulation distortion and reference spurs.

In real deployments, RFF could be most beneficial as an extra security layer on top of classic cryptography in controlled private networks (factory floors, labs, campus or government sites), where the number of radios is limited and the environment is stable. Even there, security is tricky since an insider, or a cloned unit may try to spoof a legitimate device with the same hardware and signal. We want a model that not only separates known devices but also does not wrongly push an unseen one into the “closest” known class. This leads to the open-set problem.

Focus on the open set challenge

Among the existing ML challenges present in literature, we decided to focus on the open set challenge as motivated earlier.

In traditional RFF identification, a classifier is trained on signals from a fixed set of devices, each assigned to its own class label. The model is then evaluated on these same known classes, which defines the closed-set classification problem: any new transmission at inference time is forced into one of the enrolled device classes.

However, in open-set environments, unauthorized or previously unseen devices may appear. To handle such cases, systems must determine whether a signal belongs to one of the known (enrolled) devices or to an unknown source, which is treated as an anomaly class. This is known as an open set recognition problem.

Thus, from a Machine Learning perspective, a close-set scenario should be tackled as a classification task over the enrolled device classes, while the open-set scenario (more complex and extended scenario, closer to reality) should be tackled by extending this to include an additional anomaly class for unknown devices.

Figure 11: Close-set vs. open-set paradigms

5.5.1 Finalized Component and Prototype Status

Experimental setup and data description

To develop and evaluate the close and open set scenarios we used an in-house python-controlled SDR-based hardware platform as schematized below:

Figure 12: Experimental setup.

We are using three different transmitters:

- one Ettus USRP B210 software defined radio,
- two Ettus USRP B205mini-I software defined radio.

All three transmitters are connected to Keysight RF switch inputs. We connect an Ettus USRP B210 SDR to the output of the switch, preceded by a 30dB attenuator to protect the receiver hardware. The radio link is being wired to remove the channel effects which would add another layer of complexity to the ML task and thus could divert the focus from the primary ML problem under consideration and alter our conclusions. The TX and RX SDRs and the RF switch are controlled using an in-house python dashboard, which loads the IQ files to transmit, configures the selected SDR for transmission, configures the RF switch, configures the receiver SDR and synchronously transmits and records the transmitted IQ data.

Transmitted IQ data waveforms are generated using an internal 5G NR simulator. The recorded IQ data are then sorted into datasets and transmitted to the ML dashboard for further use.

Our data collection exploited high-gain operation to push the power amplifiers into their nonlinear regimes, i.e. maximizing device-specific hardware imperfections as RF fingerprints.

We ran the wired tests with Signal-to-Noise Ratio between 10 and 50 dB. This range is realistic and close to over-the-air use. In this range the device features still stand out above the noise.

The receiver used in-band IQ with 2.5 GHz bandwidth. Out-of-band parts can also hold device cues (e.g., intermodulation), but in practice they are hard to use: automatic gain control and filters are a trade-off, strong nearby signals can disturb, and small out-of-band energy is often lost in noise.

Data preprocessing and model design

We re-used the learnt knowledge from our previous studies and in particular deliverables D4.3 regarding the influence of the model hyperparameters and architecture on the performance such as accuracy or inference latency; in our experiments, best performance was achieved by a relatively shallow, 1-dimensional Convolution Neural Network (CNN) with only a few thousand trainable parameters in the presence of 3 classes.

The Deep Learning approach allows relatively lightweight data preprocessing at training and inference compared to traditional statistical methods. It indeed consists of collecting raw IQ samples sent by each device, which are then sliced with a non-overlapping sliding window of length 256 (i.e., stride = slice length): it produces examples of shape (256, 2) where the two channels are I and Q values are stacked together. At training, we balanced per-device slice counts, shuffled, and fed these into ML that learnt each radio's unique RF fingerprint; we also used different transmissions (batches) for the model evaluation to prevent data leakage.

Figure 13: Overview of the data preprocessing hyperparameters

Figure 14: Overview of the ML pipeline at inference

5.5.2 Achieved KPIs

Results - Closed set scenario

In the closed set scenario, we trained a classifier to distinguish among three device classes: a single B210 (Device 1) and two B205s (Devices 2 and 3). Because Devices 2 and 3 are identical hardware, we expect the error rate between those two to be higher than between either B205 or the distinct B210. The B210's unique characteristics should be easier to separate from the B205 pair.

The results are shown in Figure 13, where the accuracy/loss curves over epochs (left), the confusion matrix (middle) and a t-SNE embedding of the learned features (right) are presented. Overall, the model achieves about 97 % accuracy. The confusion matrix confirms perfect (100 %) classification of Device 1 and roughly 96 % accuracy when distinguishing between Devices 2 and 3. The loss curves plummet in the first ten epochs and then flatten out, while accuracy rises just as rapidly before settling around 97 %. In the t-SNE plot visualizing the extracted features from the said model in three dimensions, three compact clusters emerge for the 3 classes: Device 1 is tightly separated, and although Devices 2 and 3 lie closer together - reflecting their similar hardware - they remain distinct enough to support a classification performance higher than 90%.

Figure 15: Results of the closed set scenario

Results - Open set scenario

In the presence of these 3 devices (2 B205s, 1 B210) coming from 2 different device types / “families” (B205 vs. B210), 2 possibilities / combinations were offered to us when implementing the open set scenario:

- “Easy” open set scenario: attack with the B210 device (unknown at training) and use the two B205 devices for the training,
- “Hard” open set scenario: attack with one of the B205 devices (unknown at training) and use the second B205 device and the single B210 for the training.

For both open set scenarios, we set up a novel ML anomaly detection pipeline which was able to successfully identify the unknown device as an attacker.

About the temperature effect

While conducting our ML studies on open- and closed-set scenarios, we have observed a temperature drift, as indicated on Figure 15. One can see in the graph the classification accuracy of our ML model (Y-axis) for two classes vs. device temperature (X-axis). Here, the model was trained on the data issued from two warmed-up devices, as they are transmitting data in large batches at maximum power, heating up the hardware. The classification accuracy is obtained while inferring that same trained model on different temperature data - dataset which has been collected post-training in a temperature chamber using the same two devices as the ones employed during training. Clearly, an accuracy drop due to the temperature drift is observed, showing a 50% accuracy of the model for the data below 25-30°C which is equal to a random decision making in the presence of a binary classification (i.e. only 2 classes).

Figure 16: The classification accuracy of our ML model (Y-axis) vs. device temperature (X-axis)

Understanding and controlling the temperature drift is essential for the robustness on the ML model, which should operate in the same domain during the training and the inference for the best performance. A new ML approach has been developed in the project to tackle the problem, and a patent application has been filed on that.

5.5.3 Component/partner Interactions and Input to WP6

Governed by the Project Consortium Agreement, here is a list of collaborations with partners:

Collaboration with Nokia Bell Labs

We received several batches of IQ data transmitted over-the-air to check the influence of the channel and the distance to the receiver on the model performance.

Collaboration with NXP

We received wired, PA-only IQ datasets from seven NXP power amplifiers; NXP also provided versions with additive Gaussian noise to emulate receiver noise.

Collaboration with BI

Our ONNX-format model has been shared with BI to experiment running the inference on their M3 platform.

5.5.4 Research Outlook / Road to product

In both closed-set and open-set evaluations, our approach proved consistently to be robust and reliable. Carefully lightweighted, tuned and calibrated, our 1D CNN extracted highly discriminative embeddings with neither overfitting nor underfitting: training and validation losses converged smoothly, and we achieved average accuracies above 95% even when distinguishing very similar devices from the same hardware family. To catch unknown transmitters, we set up a novel ML anomaly detection pipeline - which has been validated as part of the WP6 - and was able to correctly flag an unknown device as an attacker. Overall, this work demonstrates that, with smart data collection, balanced model capacity, and calibrated anomaly detection, radio-frequency fingerprinting can achieve both high accuracy and robust performance under the given experimental conditions.

6 Conclusion

This deliverable has presented the final results of **Work Package 4 (WP4)**, bringing together the heterogeneous accelerators and orchestration mechanisms that were designed to make the COREnext platform both efficient and trustworthy. The purpose of this report was to consolidate the status of all digital components, summarize the achieved KPIs, document the interactions and cooperations between partners, and provide a clear outlook both for further research and for product development.

The digital components reported here span the full RAN processing chain. On the one hand, the RISC-V-based acceleration components address the computationally most demanding parts of the low-PHY, high-PHY, and MAC layers, combining programmable flexibility with the efficiency of specialized hardware. On the other hand, the isolation and orchestration mechanisms provide the means to share, manage, and secure these resources across heterogeneous many-cores, FPGAs, and networked devices. Taken together, these components form the backbone of the COREnext digital platform: accelerators provide raw performance and efficiency, while orchestration ensures that this performance can be harnessed securely and reliably in multi-tenant, large-scale 6G environments. This combination directly supports the use cases identified in D2.1: efficient acceleration is critical to meet the latency, and throughput demands of XR applications, orchestration and trust mechanisms address the safety and reliability needs of automotive and industrial automation, and scalability with strong security is indispensable for smart city infrastructures with millions of connected devices.

Throughout this final reporting period, the components showed measurable progress. Many **KPIs** were improved compared to earlier prototypes, and several new KPIs were achieved for the first time. These results confirm that the chosen architectural directions – open, extensible RISC-V designs for acceleration and hardware-based isolation for trustworthiness – are both technically feasible and effective. The detailed KPI tables included in this deliverable provide quantitative evidence for these advances.

Equally important, WP4 fostered numerous **cooperations** between partners, with components being co-designed, integrated, and evaluated across institutional boundaries. This tight collaboration demonstrates that the COREnext approach is not a collection of isolated technical results, but a coherent and interlinked platform. These strong partner interactions will prove particularly beneficial for WP6, where multiple components will be brought together in demonstrators that reflect realistic 6G use cases.

A key element of this deliverable is the **research outlook**. For each component, plans for further scientific and technical work were outlined, ranging from advancing compiler toolchains for RISC-V accelerators, to refining virtualization and microkernel mechanisms, to extending trust management and authentication schemes for IoT and radio links. At the same time, clear **roads to product** were identified, showing how the prototypes can evolve into commercially relevant solutions. This dual perspective highlights the broader significance of the work: the components are not only academic contributions that advance the state of the art, but also concrete enablers for industrial exploitation.

In summary, WP4 has successfully delivered a set of digital components that embody the COREnext principles of efficiency and trustworthiness by design. They represent key building blocks of the overall system architecture defined in WP3 and respond directly to the requirements identified in WP2. With the conclusion of this work, the focus now shifts towards WP6 and WP7, where the integration into demonstrators and the definition of exploitation strategies will ensure that the technical achievements of WP4 have lasting impact.